

3RD EUROCC VILNIUS WORKSHOP ON USING HPC

Abstract book

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Program

Monday, January 20

13:00–13:30	REGISTRATION	
13:30–14:00	WELCOME WORDS	
13:30–14:00	Mindaugas Mačernis	EuroHPC supercomputers, quantum computers and calls for computing
14:00–14:25	Stepas Toliautas	HPC training in the EuroCC network: activities, initiatives, opportunities
14:25–14:45	Laura Baliulytė	Theoretical study of TPPS4 aggregation
14:45–15:00	Egidijus Vilčiauskas	Hydration free energy calculations using molecular dynamics for trans-stilbene and other compounds
15:00–15:30	COFFEE BREAK	
15:30–15:50	Jogilė Mačytė	Importance of anharmonic calculations for the assignment of the vibrational bands of butyric acid
15:50–16:05	Goda Bankovskaitė	Modeling Raman and absorption spectra of carotenoids of various lengths using density functional theory and molecular dynamics
16:05–16:30	COFFEE BREAK	
16:30–18:00	DISCUSSIONS ON USING HPC (MODERATOR Mindaugas Mačernis)	

Tuesday, January 21

8:00–9:00	REGISTRATION	
9:00–9:40	Bruno Robert (Keynote speaker)	Modelling carotenoid properties
9:40–10:10	COFFEE BREAK	
10:10–10:30	Lukas Razinkovas (Invited speaker)	Vibrationally resolved optical lineshapes of semiconductor deep-level defects
10:30–10:50	Žyginta Murnikova	Peptide in ionic liquid mixtures with water – theoretical study of structure and NMR spectra
10:50–11:10	Austėja Mikalčiūtė	Complete non-adiabatic exciton Hamiltonian for photosynthetic pigment–protein complexes
11:10–11:30	Gabrielė Rankelytė	Impact of protein geometry and protonation pattern on the excited states of pigments in photosynthetic complexes
11:30–13:00	PHOTO & LUNCH	
13:00–13:20	Stepas Toliautas	Simulation of molecular sensor insertion into a lipid membrane
13:20–13:40	Valdas Jonauskas	Theoretical study of electron-impact ionization for Ne^{2+} , Ne^{3+} , and Ne^{4+}
13:40–14:00	Yaraslau Padrez	Towards an automated diagnosis of well-differentiated thyroid carcinomas based on wide field second harmonic generation microscopy imaging
14:00–14:20	Vytautas Bubilaitis	Molecular aggregates at various intensities of optical fields: from absorption to six-wave mixing 2DES

14:20–15:00	COFFEE BREAK	
15:00–15:20	Simona Streckaitė	Quantum cutting in ytterbium doped perovskites
15:20–15:40	Einaras Sipavičius	Nanoorganization in aqueous mixtures of choline lysinate studied by NMR and molecular dynamics / quantum mechanics modelling
15:40–16:00	Alytis Gruodis	Derivatives of Enamines as p-type Semiconductors. Structure and Energetics using QC approach
16:00–16:20	Jelena Tamulienė	Modeling and investigation of high-energy materials
16:20–16:40	Mindaugas Mačernis	Challenges in modeling molecular aggregates using HPC: insights from molecular dynamics and density functional theory
17:00–20:00	NETWORKING / DINNER	

Welcome

We are pleased to welcome you to the 3rd EuroCC Vilnius workshop on HPC usage, organized by the Lithuanian National Competence Centre (NCC Lithuania) under the EuroCC4SEE project. This two-day event will cover various research topics utilizing High-Performance Computing (HPC) resources, including the Vilnius University supercomputer 'VU HPC' Saulėtekis at the Faculty of Physics and EuroHPC facilities. Topics will range from astrophysics to quantum chemistry and molecular dynamics, alongside discussions on potential academia-industry collaborations. We wish you inspiring presentations, fruitful discussions, and enjoyable networking opportunities.

The Organizers

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EuroHPC supercomputers, quantum computers and calls for computing

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The Lithuanian National Competence Centre (NCC Lithuania), organized by EuroHPC under the European Commission (Fig. 1), serves as the central contact point for HPC and related technologies such as AI, HPDA and Quantum Computing in Lithuania. [1,2]. The missions are to:

- Develop and display a comprehensive and transparent map of HPC competences and institutions [1,2].
- Act as a gateway for industry and academia to providers with suitable expertise, help to get HPC resources [3].
- Collect HPC training offers [4] and display them in a central place together with international training offers collected by other NCCs and HPC Centres of Excellences (CoEs) [5].
- Foster the industrial uptake of HPC [2-4].

Fig. 1. NCC Lithuania logo

The activities of NCC Lithuania are coordinated by the Faculty of Physics at Vilnius University, with partners including the Faculty of Mathematics and Informatics at Vilnius University, Vilnius TECH, the KTU Artificial Intelligence Center, and the Lithuanian Hydrometeorological Service [2].

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Theoretical study of TPPS₄ aggregation

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Water-soluble, metal-free, highly stable aggregates are important as possible theranostic agents for photoacoustic imaging (PAI) and for photodynamic therapy (PDT) due to the intense light absorption in the phototherapeutic window. The 5,10,15,20-tetrakis(4-sulfonatophenyl) porphyrin (TPPS₄) molecules absorb light and initiate the activation processes leading to the death of the tumor cells, hence, could be used in PDT [1]. The monomers of TPPS₄ efficiently self-associate into large J-aggregates (side-by-side) or H-aggregates (face-to-face) in aqueous media depending on the concentration of TPPS₄ molecules and pH value of the solution. It is still not clear what type of aggregates are formed in specific conditions. Due to this reason we investigate how tetramers could be formed.

The goal of this study is to determine the most stable zwitterionic TPPS₄ tetramers. QM geometry optimization of the zwitterionic TPPS₄ Z1 and Z2 monomers was performed to determine molecular configuration using DFT B3LYP with Pople 6-311G(d,p) basis set. The Gaussian 16 C.01 program [2] was used. The next step was to take parameters from the GAFF. It was also adjusted several parameters of monomers. MM geometry optimization was also performed. Z1 and Z2 tetramers were constructed and solvated in box of water before MD simulation. MD simulation was also performed. In this research, the AMBER 22 [3] program was used.

We performed QM and MM optimizations of the TPPS₄ Z1 and Z2 monomers. The GAFF description of these monomers was revised. Two linear TPPS₄ Z1 and Z2 tetramers were constructed and their MD simulation was performed. The intermolecular curvature angle of these tetramers were calculated. It was determined that TPPS₄ Z1 and Z2 tetramers tend to curl into circle.

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Hydration free energy calculations using molecular dynamics for trans-stilbene and other compounds

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Organic molecules like diarylethylenes, exemplified by stilbene, are valued for their unique photochemical properties, including *trans-cis* isomerization and fluorescence lifetime variability, making them promising components for highly sensitive sensing applications. The structural Stilbene complexes modeling requires molecular dynamics (MD) analysis [1]. Understanding of free energy calculations with MD simulations in context of other data provides insight into the reliability and accuracy of such methods.

In this work we present an overview of different ways for calculating hydration free energies while comparing our results against the FreeSolv database [2] and sources found within. Considering a thermal noise of 2.47 kJ/mol, we conclude that our findings correlate well with both experimental values calculated by other (non-MD) means (Fig. 1.) and with the findings of the Mobley group. Eight molecules were tested using two different methods, with different simulation lengths and solvated using different water models. The resulting difference in free energy values when using TIP4P or SPC/E water models is not significant and as such it is recommended to use the simpler and more efficient SPC/E model for further studies. We also find that extending the simulation length (BAR) past 10 ns and into 20 ns produces little change in the final value but significantly reduces the error. WHAM simulations are more efficient when computing resources are limited but are more prone to crashing and require multiple simulations to estimate an error value. All methods produce free energy values that are within 3 kJ/mol of each other (Fig. 2.). Default GROMACS simulation parameters results in producing accurate data.

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Fig. 1. Calculated free energies (Y-axis) against Experimental values (X-axis).

Fig. 2. Hydration free energies for trans-stilbene.

Importance of Anharmonic Calculations for the Assignment of the Vibrational Bands of Butyric Acid

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Butyric acid, or butanoic acid, is a short-chain saturated carboxylic acid [1]. Carboxylic acids are organic compounds that include one or more carboxyl groups, and their chemical and biochemical properties strongly depend on the length of the carbon chain, molecular structure, and presence of additional functional groups [2]. The main objective of this work is to perform conformational analysis of butyric acid using high-level quantum chemical calculations and low-temperature matrix isolation infrared absorption spectroscopy. The results are presented in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Infrared absorption spectra of butyric acid: (a) experimental spectrum in argon matrix, (b) experimental spectrum in neon matrix together with theoretically in harmonic and anharmonic approximations calculated spectra of the TTT and $G^{\pm}TT$ conformers

Geometry optimization and calculations of the fundamental vibrations for three staggered conformers of butyric acid were carried out using Density Functional Theory (DFT) with the B3LYP functional and Møller-Plesset perturbation theory (MP2) approaches. In both cases, the same cc-pVTZ basis set was employed, and the vibrational frequencies were calculated using both harmonic and anharmonic methods. Our study shows that three stable conformers of butyric acid molecules are trapped in argon and neon matrices. It was found that anharmonic calculations are extremely useful for identifying Fermi resonance experimental spectral bands. These calculations allow for a more accurate assignment of spectral bands in the C=O stretch vibration region, with the origin and behavior of these bands upon matrix annealing correctly identified only after employing anharmonic calculations at the MP2 level.

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Modeling Raman and Absorption Spectra of Carotenoids of Various Lengths Using Density Functional Theory and Molecular Dynamics

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Carotenoids are naturally occurring pigments that perform many essential functions in nature [1,2]. They play a critical role in photosynthesis, performing light harvesting and photoprotective functions. Carotenoids are responsible for the coloration of leaves, fruits, flowers, and other organisms. The photophysics of carotenoids can be understood by examining polyene molecules. The study of carotenoid excited-state energies and structures is necessary for a deeper understanding of light absorption processes driven by chlorophylls, carotenoids, and other pigments. However, Raman and absorption dynamics still is unclear [1,2] and here were present three main results for Raman study, Forbidden state modeling and complex search from Molecular Dynamics (MD)

We investigated LYC/ β -CD complexes (Fig. 1) using MD and by comparing the results with experimental Raman data for LYC/HP-CD. We demonstrate that the Raman ν_1 mode shifts to either lower or higher frequencies depending on lycopene's position within the β -CD.

Using density functional theory (DFT), we calculate the structures and Raman spectra of various carotenoids and polyenes. We described energy diagrams of low-lying excited states with respect to Raman ν_1 band using DFT and the ADC(n) family of correlated excited state methods (Fig. 2).

MD calculations were performed on fucoxanthin in polar solvent by using methanol molecules. The properties of the lowest active excited states were evaluated. For this task QM/MM approach is established by using DFT methods. We find that the lowest optically allowed transition shifts to lower energies. New states with $f > 0.1$ have not been identified.

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This work was partially supported by the Research Council of Lithuania (Grant No. S-MIP-23-48). Computations were performed on resources of the supercomputer "VU HPC" Saulėtekis in Vilnius University at Faculty of Physics.

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Fig. 1. Lycopene complex with β -cyclodextrin.

Fig. 2. Energy diagram for the low-lying singlet excited states of polyenes (N = 2–10).

Fig. 3. Fucoxanthin QM/MM simulation

Modelling Carotenoid Properties

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Carotenoid molecules are essential molecules in all kingdoms of biology. In plants, these linear, highly conjugated molecules are important constituents of the light-harvesting system, and also play a (photo)protective role at the level of the photosynthesis apparatus and the chloroplast membranes. They confer their colour to fruits and flowers, and some of their breakdown products control plant growth as hormones or confer them scent. In animals, among other molecules, vitamin A, important for vision and immune system, and retinol, an essential driver of foetal development are produced from carotenoids.

Structure of β -carotene

In the last decade, we have developed computing strategies to model the electronic and vibrational properties of carotenoids, which underlie their biological activity with a dual goal. First we aimed at determining the relationship between the structure and the main electronic properties of these molecules, and this led us to reconsider the conjugation structure of these molecules. Second, we wanted to understand the variety of carotenoid present in Nature: there are about many hundreds of different carotenoids present in different organisms, and the reason for such a diversity of molecule is not known. On at least two classes of these molecules, we could determine how additional groups grafted to the conjugated chain could influence their configuration, and thus how they could be selective for these molecules to their protein binding sites.

Vibrationally Resolved Optical Lineshapes of Semiconductor Deep-Level Defects

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Optically active deep-level semiconductor defects have become building blocks for numerous quantum technologies, such as quantum computing, sensing, and communication. This presentation delves into theoretical modeling techniques for simulating and interpreting the optical spectra of these defects [1,2]. Special attention is given to transitions involving degenerate electronic states, where electronic degeneracy often induces the dynamical Jahn-Teller effect - a phenomenon arising from intricate interactions between electronic and vibrational degrees of freedom. The discussion will highlight the application of advanced theoretical methods to unravel these complex effects and practical computational strategies to model the optical properties of such systems accurately.

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Peptide in Ionic Liquid Mixtures with Water – Theoretical Study of Structure and NMR spectra

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Ionic liquids (ILs) have been known as “green” and biocompatible solvents for quite some time and some of their possible biological uses include changing catalytic activity of enzymes, stabilizing or destabilizing various proteins, as well as making them permeate more easily through membranes [1]. The nature of ILs and proteins interactions varies and is difficult to evaluate, so smaller peptides are often used as a model system to discover how different ILs interact with said peptides and change their structure in the aqueous solution. The method most suited for recognizing intermolecular interactions is nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy as atoms, especially hydrogen, chemical shift is very sensitive to changes of central molecule’s close environment.

Fig. 1. Structural formulas of a) peptide Ala-Glu-Pro-Phe, b) ethyl-3-methylimidazolium trifluoroacetate, c) 1,3-dimethylimidazolium dimethyl phosphate.

In this work an Ala-Glu-Pro-Phe tetrapeptide was investigated using molecular dynamics (MD) simulations and quantum mechanics/molecular mechanics calculations, while in an aqueous environment and in IL/water mixture. Two ILs were chosen, both with popular imidazolium cations – ethyl-3-methylimidazolium trifluoroacetate ([Emim][TFA]) and 1,3-dimethylimidazolium dimethyl phosphate ([Mmim][DMP]). Theoretically computed chemical shift differences of peptide’s hydrogen atoms were compared to experimental results [2] allowing us to evaluate the different interactions taking place in peptide/IL/water systems, while MD simulation data revealed some structural changes in the peptide’s structure itself.

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Complete Non-adiabatic Exciton Hamiltonian for Photosynthetic Pigment-Protein Complexes

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One of the core processes of photosynthesis is the “collection of light” through multi-pigment light-harvesting antenna complexes. A vast diversity of photosynthetic pigments and light-harvesting complexes has evolved, what adapted the process to occur both in water and on land and it can be found in many bacteria, algae and plant species. In this work, we extend the standard exciton model typically used to calculate the Hamiltonian of the light-harvesting complexes. We incorporate the novel environment-induced non-adiabatic inter-molecular couplings and use the resulting Hamiltonian to calculate the variation of absorption spectra of two different light-harvesting complexes: Fenna-Matthews-Olson and fucoxanthin-chlorophyll binding protein using their crystallographic protein structures. To achieve this, pigments ground and first two excited states were modeled at QM level using GAUSSIAN¹ software with DFT/TD-DFT methodology with CAM-B3LYP functional and 6-31G(d) basis set, while their transition energies were adjusted due to electrostatic interaction with proteins. The non-adiabatic excitonic Hamiltonian was then used to calculate exciton relaxation rates, their lifetimes and the absorption spectra of the complexes. Spectra of pigments *in vacuo*, in a protein environment with different force-fields and in a protein environment with addition of ions in case of adiabatic and non-adiabatic (including ground state of pigments) couplings were compared. The results demonstrate that the excitonic non-adiabatic amplitudes lead to finite exciton lifetime, they shift absorption spectra to higher energies and induce variation of the spectral shape.

Fig. 1. FMO pigment-protein complex structure.

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Impact of Protein Geometry and Protonation Pattern on the Excited States of Pigments in Photosynthetic Complexes

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PSI is the most efficient light-to-energy conversion apparatus where almost all light, absorbed by the light harvesting antenna LHCI, is converted to chemical energy [1] through the series of reactions and energy transactions. The excitation dynamics in LHCI is highly affected by the charge-transfer (CT) states that occur between the pigments. Known CT sites in LHCI do not completely explain the spectral properties of this antenna suggesting the presence of more CT states. The energy of these states is affected by the surrounding environment (pigments and the protein). We investigated the LHCI of PSI complex structure [2] (Fig. 1). Properties of the excited states of the pigments were calculated using "VU HPC" Saulėtekis supercomputer. Charge-density coupling method [3] was used to evaluate excited state energy shifts, caused by the electrostatic environment. Our recent findings demonstrate the sensitivity of pigment excited state properties to changes in the surrounding environmental geometry. Besides the geometry, amino acids can change their protonation state as well affecting the charge distribution within the protein chain and the contribution of each part to the shift of the pigment energies.

Fig. 1. Lhca1-Lhca4 sub-complexes of LHCI, matched on top of each other (PDB ID: 5L8R, chains 1-4).

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Simulation of molecular sensor insertion into a lipid membrane

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A recently-synthesized variant of boron-dipyrromethene (BODIPY)-based class of prospective molecular sensors, BODIPY-PM, was shown to preferentially aggregate in artificial and natural cell membranes [1]. To study the mechanism of sensor insertion and stabilization, molecular dynamics (MD) model containing the sensor, bilayer lipid membrane and water surroundings was constructed and run for a total simulation time of 450 ns [2]. The simulation confirmed successful sensor insertion into the membrane with two possible orientations, depending on the membrane properties (Fig. 1). Part of the computations was performed on resources at the supercomputer "VU HPC" of Vilnius University in Faculty of Physics location [3].

Fig. 1. Chemical structure of BODIPY-PM molecule (*left*) and evolution of the distance of its main functional groups from the center plane of a bilayer lipid membrane, as obtained by MD simulation (*right*).

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Theoretical study of electron-impact ionization for Ne^{2+} , Ne^{3+} , and Ne^{4+}

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Electron-impact single ionization process for the Ne^{2+} , Ne^{3+} , and Ne^{4+} ions is investigated as a result of direct and indirect ionization processes. The ionization is analyzed for all energy levels of the ground configurations. The excitation-autoionization (EA) process is the strongest indirect ionization process for the studied ions. EA is initiated by electron-impact excitation to intermediate autoionizing state that subsequently decays to next charge state through autoionization process. However, the produced autoionizing state also can decay through radiative transitions, by this, reducing population of ions transferred to higher ionization stage.

The distorted wave (DW) approximation, implemented in the Flexible Atomic Code (FAC) [1], is used to study collisional ionization and excitation cross sections. Direct ionization (DI) and excitations are analyzed from the 2s and 2p subshells of the ground configurations of the neon ions. The excitations up to shells with the principal quantum numbers $n \leq 20$ are included in the study.

The scaling factors for the DW cross sections are used to explain measurements for the Ne^{2+} and Ne^{3+} ions since the DW approximation overestimates experimental data. Additionally, the single ionization threshold value provided by NIST is integrated into the study to derive the final ionization cross sections for Ne^{2+} .

The EA process accounts for $\sim 16\%$ of the total ionization cross sections from the ground state of the Ne^{2+} ion. What is more, the EA channels provide $\sim 24\%$ for the $^1\text{S}_0$ level of Ne^{2+} . For the $^1\text{D}_2$ level of Ne^{2+} , the indirect ionization process gives $\sim 21\%$.

The EA process contributes $\sim 8\%$ of the total electron-impact ionization cross sections for the ground level of the Ne^{3+} ion. Slightly higher contribution of EA is obtained for ^2D ($\sim 12\%$) and ^2P ($\sim 18\%$) terms of the ground configuration.

Our investigation of single ionization cross sections for the Ne^{4+} ion using the DW approximation shows a good agreement with experimental data for the four lowest energy levels of the ground configuration [3]. Excitations from the 2p subshell produce configurations that lie below the ionization threshold of Ne^{4+} and therefore do not contribute to the single ionization process. The indirect ionization process contributes $\sim 12\%$ to the total ionization cross sections for the ground level. The DI 2p channel remains the dominant ionization pathway across all studied ions.

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Towards an automated diagnosis of well-differentiated thyroid carcinomas based on wide field second harmonic generation microscopy imaging

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Papillary thyroid carcinoma (PTC) and follicular thyroid carcinoma (FTC) are both well-differentiated tumors and together account for up to 88% of all cases of thyroid cancer [1]. The collagen capsule surrounding PTC or FTC nodules is an important histopathologic feature that provides valuable information about the malignancy, invasiveness of the tumor, and prognosis for cure. Wide field second harmonic generation microscopy enables label-free, rapid visualization of collagen networks in cancer tissue sections on centimeter-sized areas with submicrometer resolution. Applying machine learning algorithms to the large datasets of SHG images can help identify specific features associated with either PTC or FTC, enabling accurate diagnosis of well-differentiated thyroid carcinomas. In the present study, we applied three monolithic (logistic regression, RG; C-support vector classifier, C-SVC; and a multilayer perceptron MLP) and three ensemble (random forest, RF; eXtreme gradient boosting, XGBoost and light gradient-boosting machine, LightGBM) classifiers to (i) diagnose PTC and FTC based on the texture features of SHG images of collagen networks in the whole scans of thyroid tissue sections, (ii) analyze how the heterogeneity of collagen structure within the capsules and the similarities between PTC and FTC affect the prediction performance of the models, and (iii) to evaluate the feasibility of SHG-based discrimination between PTC and FTC. Three different approaches were applied to pre-process the data, aiming at accurate selection of collagenous structures for training and testing the models. The best performance was achieved by the C-SVC, MLP and XGBoost models with accuracies of 84.73%, 81.76% and 81.42%, respectively, when forming the training and validation sets considering the heterogeneity of the capsules as a whole, with the C-SVC model showing the best classification performance on the completely unknown dataset. Similarities in the textural features of PTC and FTC nodules and the heterogeneity of collagen structures throughout the capsule complicate the diagnosis of PTC and FTC. The developed predictive models can serve as a reliable complement to histopathologic examinations to enable accurate diagnosis.

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Molecular aggregates at various intensities of optical fields: from absorption to six-wave mixing 2DES

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Perturbative expansion in powers to the excitation field is a powerful tool for non-linear spectra analysis. While such an approach allows to calculate induced polarization at an arbitrary order. It fails to account for nonlinear processes that react to change in optical field intensity such as exciton – exciton annihilation (EEA).

EEA is an excitation density dependent process as it involves 2 separate excitations interacting and forming a short lived doubly excited state. This state quickly decays and only a single excitation remains. The effect is a nonlinear decay in excitation density.

One way to treat this problem is by using nonlinear exciton equations (NEE) which allows to generate hierarchy of equations. The hierarchy is endless and needs to be cut at some point either by dropping terms (with reasoning that EEA limits the number of excitations in the system) or factorizing them in lower order terms while preserving the dependence on optical field intensity.

We have expanded the NEE equation with EEA terms[1]. We compared a few factorizations that should simplify calculations, but it was only for a molecular dimer. Since then we have made several developments. The equations were expanded to generalized(from paulion to boson) particles[2]. NEE were applied to study EEA signatures in 2D electron spectra calculations with up to six-wave mixing [3]. We made studies of the effects of various factorizations schemes on larger aggregates with varying excitation intensity [4] and additional possible simplifications to the NEE [2].

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Quantum cutting in ytterbium doped perovskites

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Ytterbium-doped cesium lead halide perovskites exhibit unusual down-conversion with quantum efficiencies exceeding 100% [1-2]. This phenomenon has been attributed to quantum cutting (QC) when a perovskite exciton (~500 nm) is converted into two Yb³⁺ excitations (~1000 nm). However, the mechanism of energy transfer from the perovskite to the Yb³⁺ ions is still debated, and it is still unclear what processes limit the energy conversion efficiency.

In this work, 0-50% Yb-doped CsPbX₃ (X: Cl⁻, Br⁻, or both) perovskite powders prepared by mechanosynthesis were investigated. X-ray diffraction (XRD), transmission electron microscopy (TEM) and electron paramagnetic resonance (EPR) measurements confirmed the formation of a standard perovskite structure and the incorporation of ytterbium into the perovskite matrix. To investigate optical properties of prepared powders and to evaluate the limiting factors of QC efficiency, low temperature time-resolved fluorescence spectroscopy together with microscopic studies were applied.

We demonstrate that two types of ytterbium species are formed, depending on the concentration of Yb³⁺ in the perovskite. The photoluminescence (PL) of Yb³⁺ shows a biexponential decay at low concentrations, attributed to the presence of monomeric and dimeric Yb³⁺ species. The fast decay component is attributed to monomeric Yb³⁺ ions, which do not perform QC and have low PL yield. This component disappears when the concentration of Yb increases to about 5% and PL of dimeric species dominates. The PL decay becomes faster again when the concentration of Yb³⁺ exceeds 10%, due to migration limited excitation quenching. These two processes are important factors limiting QC efficiency.

Fig. 1. NIR PL kinetics of Yb-doped CsPbX₃ perovskites with different Yb³⁺ concentrations.

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Nanoorganization in aqueous mixtures of choline lysinate studied by NMR and molecular dynamics / quantum mechanics modelling

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Choline lysinate (ChoLys) is a biocompatible ionic liquid (IL) that belongs to the family of choline-amino acid ILs (ChoAA). ChoAA ionic liquids have a capability to solubilize various drugs and other organic compounds (i.e. lignin in biomass processing) even when a small amount of IL is added to the water [1]. These properties are associated with complex intermolecular structure of ChoAA and water mixtures, ranging from small clusters of water surrounded by IL to intact network of water molecules, with a possible intermediate state – formation of water nanopackets (nanometer scaled clusters of water molecules) [1].

This study is aimed at structural characterization of ChoLys:water mixtures using a combination of molecular dynamics (MD) simulations and quantum mechanics / molecular mechanics calculations (QM/MM). This approach allows not only to characterize the intermolecular structure, but it also involves calculation of ¹H NMR shielding constants and validation of simulated structure by comparing calculated values to experimental data.

MD simulations of six ChoLys:H₂O mixtures, ranging from 0,025 % to 50 % ChoLys molar fraction, were simulated using „Amber“ package. Intermolecular structure was characterized by radial distribution functions between various atomic pairs, including N and O in Cho⁺, O, N_α and N_ε in Lys⁻ and O in H₂O. All these species participate in hydrogen bonding, forming a complex intermolecular network. Water cluster size distribution analysis showed that two water clusterization regimes (small clusters and water network) manifest in simulated trajectories. Trends of calculated diffusion coefficients support this result. Finally, ¹H NMR shielding constants were calculated for Cho⁺ CH₂ groups, Lys H_α, H_β and H_ε and water (H_w) protons. Results partially match with experimental data, with H_α and H_β trends (with respect to variation of molar composition) being exceptionally accurate.

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Fig. 1. ChoLys structural formula with positions in Lys⁻ anion denoted using Greek letters.

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Derivatives of Enamines as *p*-type Semiconductors.

Structure and Energetics using QC approach

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Organic hole-transporting materials (HTMs) are important as a photo-voltaic sensor for different purposes: *in vivo* sensors for biological systems [1], perovskite solar cells [2], etc. This work represents the investigation of structure and energetical properties of the hole transporting enamine units (central core) related to the spiro-bis-indane-based compounds by combining different aniline substituents [3], see Fig.1. Ground state energy structure and following electronic excitations were obtained using *Gaussian16* [4] package. Density functional theory (DFT) Cam-B3LYP method and 6-31G(d) basis set (supplemented with polarization functions (d)) were used for ground-state optimization that supplemented the experimental study. Due to the large volume of molecular structures, solvation effects were not considered in all cases. Semiempirical TD method (for singlets only) was used for estimation of parameters of Frank-Condon type transition and corresponding charge redistribution. Several molecular realizations of promised conformers are presented in Fig. 2. Substituents are oriented in a chaotic manner resulting in a vast array of different conformers. All structures were derived using the *grad-optimization* technique, ensuring convergence of all parameters such as Maximum Force, RMS Force, Maximum Displacement and RMS Displacement. Both HTMs exhibited high thermal stability and relatively high hole-drift mobility, making them viable candidates for application as HTMs.

Fig. 1. Structures of HTMs V1476 and V1481.

Fig. 2. Most promised conformers of V1476 (a) and V1481 (b).

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Modeling and investigation of high-energy materials

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The global market for high-energy materials has been consistently growing [1]. Between 2017 and 2022, it expanded from nearly USD 23.8 billion to USD 31.2 billion, and in 2024, the global explosives market reached a volume of approximately 16.58 million metric tons [2]. This growth is primarily driven by the use of these materials in mining, quarrying, and construction industries. From a practical perspective, an energetic compound should be powerful, stable, insensitive to mechanical stimuli, and capable of releasing a substantial amount of energy during intentional detonation. Consequently, the development of new functionalized compounds with unique and improved properties is essential for advancing energetic materials.

In this context, we conducted studies on various high-energy compounds with the goal of creating new materials or modifying existing ones, as well as understanding their potential risks. Our research employed Becke's three-parameter hybrid functional approach with non-local correlation provided by Lee, Yang, and Parr, combined with the cc-pVTZ basis set. This approach was used to evaluate the influence of substitutions or the formation of salts on the energetic properties of nitramines. The geometry, total energy, and heat of formation of the selected stable conformers of various materials were calculated to derive key parameters such as density, resistance to shock stimuli, detonation pressure, and velocity.

The results of our study allow us to predict new multipurpose energetic materials that achieve a good balance between energy and stability. For example, our findings indicate that compounds such as *N*-(2-nitroethyl)-*N*-(2,4,6-trinitrophenyl)nitramine, *N*-(2,4,6-trinitrophenyl)-*N*-[(3,4,5-trinitro-1*H*-pyrazol-1-yl)methyl]nitramine, *N*-(2,2-dinitroethyl)-*N*-(2,4,6-trinitrophenyl)nitramine, *N*-(2,2,2-trinitroethyl)-*N*-(2,4,6-trinitrophenyl)nitramine, and *N*-(trinitromethyl)-*N*-(2,4,6-trinitrophenyl)nitramine exhibit superior explosive properties and greater stability compared to tetryl, although they remain sensitive to shock stimuli. Based on these results, we recommend new tetryl analogs containing dinitroethyl, trinitroethyl, and trinitromethyl substituents for practical applications. Additionally, we investigated the properties of some 5-amino-3-[(2,4,6-trinitrophenyl)amino]-1*H*-1,2,4-triazole (APATO) cationic salts. The results of the energetic characterizations revealed that the synthesized salts possess enhanced energetic properties, outperforming TNT. Notably, the APATO perchlorate salt warrants special attention as a thermostable high-energy material.

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Challenges in Modeling Molecular Aggregates Using HPC: Insights from Molecular Dynamics and Density Functional Theory

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Various molecular systems, including solvents, crystals, and protein aggregates, behave according to their initial conditions, as observed in carotenoids, stilbene, and Bis(diphenylphosphino)methane (dppm), Meso-tetra(4-sulfonatophenyl) porphine (TPPS4) [1-4]. Molecular Dynamics (MD) effectively captures solvent and protein dynamics, but its limitations become evident when describing processes transitioning from solvent to crystal. Here, systems are presented in which aggregated structural properties were successfully modeled using MD simulations.

Using MD simulations, we analyzed LYC/ β -CD complexes (Fig. 1) and compared the results with experimental Raman data for LYC/HP-CD. We found that the Raman ν_1 mode exhibits frequency shifts, either lower or higher, based on the positioning of lycopene within the β -CD [1]. Notably, this reveals that β -CD enables the investigation of LYC as a monomer. However, the solid-state behavior of LYC remains an unresolved question.

TPPS4, a molecular nano-wire model, forms chiral nanotubes in acidic conditions, and our MD-based strategy identifies a probable zwitterionic tetramer structure responsible for large aggregate formation [3].

By combining Car-Parrinello Molecular Dynamics, big data analytics, and Density Functional Theory, we identified seven conformers with unique P-P through-space J-coupling properties in dppm[2].

MD simulations were conducted on fucoxanthin in a polar solvent using methanol molecules. The properties of the lowest active excited states were evaluated in various carotenoids (Fig 2.), and energy diagrams of low-lying excited states were described relative to the Raman ν_1 band using DFT and the ADC(n) family of correlated excited-state methods.

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Fig. 1. Lycopene complex with β -cyclodextrin.

Fig. 2. States and correlation with Raman ν_1 for the various length Carotenoids.